

Thermomechanical Factors in Molybdenum Field Emitter Operation and Failure

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Abstract

A thermomechanical analysis of many of the basic effects which might be expected to play a role in field emitter array breakdown is given. We find that of the "intrinsic" factors considered only the large Maxwell stresses induced by the electric field might possibly lead to failure. Direct thermal effects are always insignificant. Failure modes associated with "extrinsic" phenomena such as arcing or from tip "imperfections" such as grain boundaries have not been studied and these may also be important.

Introduction

From a technological standpoint one of the most important questions concerning field emitter arrays is their reliability. As a result, much experimental work has been directed at understanding field-emitter array failures. Apart from obvious cases, however, no clear consensus on what causes most field-emitter failures has yet been reached. One can divide the possible failure modes according to whether the failure is initiated inside the tip ("intrinsic" mechanisms) or outside the tip ("extrinsic" mechanisms). In this work we focus on the former; for a discussion of the latter see Ref. 1.

Now, it is a common belief, supported by some simulations [2], that "intrinsic" field-emitter failures result from *thermal effects*, e.g., the tip melts or it fractures as a result of thermal stress. In this work we have re-examined the possible role of thermal phenomena in "intrinsic" field emitter array breakdown by performing detailed thermal and thermomechanical simulations of molybdenum field emitters. Contrary to the common belief, we find that *thermal effects are generally not significant under normal field emitter operating conditions*. According to our simulations, under normal operating conditions no thermal runaway ever occurs and temperatures never become large enough to cause excessive thermal stress or tip melting. Instead our calculations show that the only "intrinsic" factor with the potential for producing tip failure is the Maxwell stress induced directly by the electric field. Unfortunately, until the mechanical properties of real molybdenum field-emitter tips

are better characterized (especially in plastic regimes and including tip "defects") no firmer conclusions can be reached.

Simulation Approach

For computing the temperatures and stresses experienced by a field emitter tip under operating conditions we employ the widely-used mechanical engineering code ABAQUS [3]. This code solves the equations of heat conduction and/or of elasticity using the finite-element method. It is a very flexible program and allows us to directly and easily include an accurate representation of the tip geometry along with much of the thermal physics and mechanics of the emitting tip. All of our calculations assume dc bias conditions and therefore we study steady-state behavior only.

We treat field emitter tips like those fabricated at SRI, International [4], MIT Lincoln Laboratory, LETI and PIXEL International. These tips are typically made of molybdenum, have an end radius of curvature of about 200Å and a cone

Fig. 1. Axisymmetric field emitter geometry and mesh.

angle of 15° . To facilitate electrostatics calculations, for most of our work we model this geometry using appropriately chosen hyperboloids. In Fig. 1 a typical axisymmetric tip geometry and finite-element mesh is shown along with geometrical parameters.

For computing the temperatures of the tip we use ABAQUS to solve the heat conduction equation with the known temperature-dependent thermal conductivity of molybdenum, with heat sources describing ohmic and Nottingham heating and with boundary conditions specifying a fixed temperature (300K), Stefan-Boltzmann radiation or zero heat flux as appropriate. The heat source contributions are computed within Fowler-Nordheim theory. Specifically, we i) assume a voltage bias between the cathode and a planar anode, ii) compute the electric field at the tip surface assuming space charge negligible, and then iii) find the emitted current using Fowler-Nordheim theory. We perform the electric field calculation both numerically and, for hyperboloidal tips, analytically. When the latter is possible it is to be preferred because any numerical error in the electric field is exponentially magnified in the computed current. In our Fowler-Nordheim calculations we have obtained results both with and without an image term. We favor omitting the image "correction" because in previous work [5] we showed that it greatly over-estimates the electrostatic rounding of the barrier, however, having both results provides upper and lower bounds on what would be found from a full many-body calculation. In any event, knowing the emitted current density we can estimate the current density *inside* the tip and, given the temperature-dependent resistivity, can then compute the ohmic heating. The Nottingham heating is computed in the familiar way using Fowler-Nordheim theory and we assume that all of this heat is deposited at the surface [6]. We note that both the ohmic and the Nottingham heating terms need to be computed in a fully-coupled manner since the current which produces the heating is in turn affected by the resulting temperature changes.

For the stress calculations we use ABAQUS to solve the equations of elasticity assuming a body force due to thermal expansion (thermal stresses) and a surface force associated with Maxwell stress. In general, both of these could feedback and influence the temperature (via volume changes) however this effect is unimportant, and so the thermal and mechanical calculations are effectively decoupled. Nevertheless, we have solved them simultaneously simply because ABAQUS permits this with no extra work. Finally, in one trial calculation we included the elastic anisotropy of crystalline molybdenum (assuming $\langle 111 \rangle$ orientation) and, finding it to have little effect on the results, have treated molybdenum as isotropic (with a Young's modulus of 3.26×10^{12} dynes/cm² and Poisson's ratio of 0.321) in all other calculations.

In this work we aim to provide a theoretical foundation for understanding and estimating the impact of various physical factors on reliability. We have attempted to be as comprehensive as possible in including various "intrinsic"

factors which could reasonably be expected to play a role in field emitter failure. However, in drawing conclusions from our work it is important to be aware of various sources of error. First, as noted previously, there are aspects of the problem we have not considered which could well dominate. These include both "intrinsic" factors, e.g., associated with tip defects or with processing induced stresses, and "extrinsic" factors, e.g., associated with arcing phenomena. In addition, there is error in our calculations caused by uncertainty in the material (particularly mechanical) properties of the molybdenum tip and by assumptions of Fowler-Nordheim theory (e.g., concerning the energy exchange processes during emission [6]). Lastly, numerical error is a possibility (especially, as noted above, if the electric field is computed numerically) however, having performed various standard checks on our calculations, we do not consider this likely.

Results

A. Temperature Calculations

Many of the calculations presented here are for cases in which the bias was such that the emitted current was either 0.1mA or 5mA. The former is of interest since it is believed to represent a rough threshold for failure of molybdenum tips; in this case, the maximum surface electric field is $0.9V/\text{\AA}$ (no image force) or $0.57V/\text{\AA}$ (with image force). In Fig. 2 we compare on-axis ($r=0$) temperature profiles for the two currents assuming no image force "correction." For the 5mA case we show the temperatures that result when Nottingham heating is neglected and, in qualitative agreement with Ref. 2, we find that Nottingham (and not ohmic) heating is the dominant contributor to the total heating at these current levels. A plot of the individual heating contributions (Fig. 3)

Fig. 2. Temperature increase above ambient along the field emitter axis ($r=0$).

shows this directly. However, quantitatively our results disagree strongly with those of Ref. 2: At a "failure" current of 0.1mA the maximum temperature in the tip (Fig. 2) is only 7K above ambient and so can not possibly be a cause for failure. Plotting the maximum temperatures as a function of field-emitter current (Fig. 4), we find that for the emitter of Fig. 1 ($\theta = 15^\circ$) the current must be quite large ($>10\text{mA}$) for significant temperature excursions to occur. This stable temperature behavior results because heat conduction down the tip is very efficient in removing the generated heat. (Radiation is generally negligible.) This is clearly seen in Fig. 4 where the effect of geometrical changes on the maximum tip temperatures is examined. Only in the cases of very sharp tips (cone angles less than 5°) or when currents are abnormally large, e.g., as might occur during arcing, is burn-out a possibility. We note that these effects are somewhat amplified by the fact that the thermal conductivity *decreases* with temperature. However, this amplification is not sufficient to trigger thermal runaway because both ohmic and Nottingham heating also decrease with temperature. As a final point, we remark that in Fig. 4 we have also included one result in which the image force "correction" has been included. In this case temperatures are lower for a given current because, as a result of changes in tunneling probabilities, the average energy deposited per emitted electron is reduced.

B. Stress Calculations

The small temperature rises seen in the calculations of the previous section imply that the resultant thermal stresses will be small and simulation confirms this. But of course this does not mean that the total stress is small. Additional contributors to the stress state of the field-emitter are the processing of the tip ("intrinsic" stress) and the electric field

(Maxwell stress). The processing-induced stresses, although possibly large, will not be considered further here because little is known about them (see Ref. 7 for work involving Mo thin films) and because they are not bias-dependent. Concerning the Maxwell stresses, these are worth examining because it is known that they are important in field-ion microscopy [8] (where the electric fields are similar in magnitude although opposite in sign) and also in some methods of field-emitter tip fabrication [9].

In Fig. 5 we plot the maximum value of the σ_{zz} component of the total (tensile) stress --- thermal plus Maxwell --- as a function of the maximum electric field. (Both of these maxima occur of course at the apex of the field emitter). These stresses are quite large and are dominated by the Maxwell contribution, being two orders of magnitude larger than the thermal stresses alone. Their magnitude is best appreciated by noting that they are comparable to the bulk tensile strength of molybdenum as indicated in Fig. 5. The particular values of stress that occur at the current levels of interest in this paper (as computed using Fowler-Nordheim theory) are shown in Fig. 6 where we plot the stress profiles along the field-emitter axis ($r=0$) for currents of 0.1mA and 5mA. Results computed both with and without the image "correction" are shown with the latter giving larger stresses because of the larger electric fields required to produce the given current. Note that the stresses are very large only very close to the field emitter apex. Given the size of these stresses we conclude that Maxwell stress could well be very important both in re-shaping or "seasoning" of field-emitter tips, e.g., via field-aided surface diffusion, and/or in causing field-emitter failure through mechanical fracture.

Our calculations demonstrate that the electrical forces on a field-emitter under normal operating conditions are quite large

Fig. 3. Ohmic and Nottingham contributions to heating.

Fig. 4. Maximum temperature versus tip geometry.

Fig. 5. Maximum stress versus maximum electric field.

and it is reasonable to suggest that this could have important consequences for reliability. However, to make stronger statements is necessarily much more speculative because of uncertainty in the mechanical properties of the field-emitter. First, the strength of materials in general is strongly affected by the presence of impurities, dislocations and grain boundaries. It is for this reason that the bulk tensile strength of molybdenum as given in the literature varies considerably ($4.4\text{--}13.8 \times 10^9$ dynes/cm² [10]). Secondly, the mechanical characteristics of the tip could be significantly different from the bulk behavior [7] and could be strongly influenced by surface asperities or other localized "defects." And lastly, even the small temperature increases that we compute could have important mechanical consequences. In particular, it is known that molybdenum undergoes a gradual brittle-to-ductile transition around room temperature (depending on grain size and impurities) [10]. In this connection, we note that as part of this work we have performed several calculations of temperatures and stresses in tungsten tips. The results are very similar to those of molybdenum (tungsten runs slightly cooler because of its 20% larger thermal conductivity), however, one possibly important difference is that the brittle-to-ductile transition in tungsten occurs at 500K (instead of 300K for molybdenum). This could lead to a significant difference in reliability and/or failure current given that operating tip temperatures do not get much above 300K according to our calculations.

Final Comments

In this paper we have used extensive thermomechanical calculations to argue that direct thermal effects are largely irrelevant in explaining catastrophic failure in molybdenum field-emitter tips of SRI-like design. At tip currents believed

Fig. 6. Stress profiles along the field-emitter axis.

sufficient to cause tip failure (0.1mA) no thermal runaway occurs and the temperature rises are quite small. The resultant thermal stresses are, of course, also small and are entirely insufficient to cause melting or fracture of molybdenum. However, the electric fields required to produce emission currents of this size induce Maxwell stresses which are comparable to the yield strength of molybdenum. On this basis, we conclude that the tensile Maxwell stress induced by the field perhaps together with some pre-existing material flaw may be responsible for some molybdenum field emitter tip failures.

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